

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D6.4 - JOINT AGREEMENT

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Content

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Organisation of the deliverable	9
2	Development of the Joint Agreement	10
2.1	Final version of the Joint Agreement	14
3	Final considerations	20

Executive Summary

The ePLANET project, co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme, is a Coordination and Support Action aimed at establishing a new governance framework for energy transition. This initiative leverages digital technologies to harmonise information sharing, facilitating coordinated energy transition efforts across the European public sector.

ePLANET is crucial for advancing Energy Transition (ET) within the public sector, addressing several key challenges:

- Improving coordination among local authorities and regional governments.
- Enhancing decision-making processes for ET project deployment.
- Ensuring coherence and consistency in the implementation of energy transition measures (ETM).
- Promoting the digitalisation of measures and plans.
- Facilitating an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.
- Strengthening the capacity of local authorities.

These objectives collectively support informed decision-making and the effective implementation of energy transition initiatives.

This document highlights the role of the ePLANET Joint Agreement as a tool reflecting the commitment of public authorities and other stakeholders to leverage ePLANET tools and main outcomes, supporting enhanced multi-level governance coordination for energy transition. The deliverable outlines the stages involved in developing the agreement and presents its final version.

Key findings include:

- The Joint Agreement embodies a shared vision on actions and initiatives aimed at accelerating progress towards energy transition goals. It serves as a crucial mechanism for local and regional authorities, as well as at the EU political level, to capitalise on the project outcomes.
- The Joint Agreement was carefully designed and is accessible on the ePLANET official website. It was designed in a user-friendly online format to streamline the signing process.
- Representatives from diverse local and regional authorities involved in various phases of the ePLANET project (including pilot regions, follower regions, and participants in events like Stakeholders Forums) have signed the Joint Agreement.
- The process of including the names of the signatory institutions on the ePLANET website is continuous.

List of Figures

Figure 2-1 - Webpage of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections	11
Figure 2-2 - Online form: the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections	12
Figure 2-3 - Example of dissemination of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections on social media	13
Figure 2-4 - Signatories of the Brussels Declaration of European Mayors	14
Figure 2-5 - Dedicated section for the ePLANET Joint Agreement on the project's website ..	16
Figure 2-6 - Form for the ePLANET Joint Agreement.....	17
Figure 2-7 - Current signatories of the ePLANET Joint Agreement	18
Figure 2-8 - Poster with a QR Code disseminating the ePLANET Joint Agreement.....	19

Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CIMNE	International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering
CRES	Centre for Renewable Sources and Saving
ET	Energy Transition
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
EU	European Union
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability
QR Code	Quick-Response Code
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Local and regional authorities are at the forefront of the EU's ambitious mission to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. Their decentralised governance structures, unlike centralised models, enable them to directly engage with citizens and stakeholders, fostering a grassroots clean energy transition. This bottom-up approach is crucial for accelerating the deployment of renewable energy technologies at the community level. However, realising this clean energy future hinges on effective local commitment and well-defined plans.

One significant challenge lies in the lack of coordination between local and regional authorities. This hinders optimal decision-making and consistent implementation of energy transition measures across towns and cities. Additionally, the current fragmented landscape of local authority platforms in the EU creates information silos, impeding data sharing and community engagement.

The ePLANET project addresses these challenges head-on by proposing a novel "clustering governance" approach centred on a digital framework that facilitates the sharing of harmonised information. This empowers the public sector to implement coordinated energy transition actions with greater ease.

ePLANET's main objectives are:

- To define and establish a transparent and coherent information sharing framework among public authorities.
- To deploy multi-level working groups of related public authorities and stakeholders for sharing of information and to enable a collaborative approach in development and updating of Energy Transition plans.
- To enable digitalization of the energy transition plans of the public authorities as base for coherence, sharing, coordination and integration.
- To support new adopters and consolidate existing networks.
- To institutionalize ePLANET networks and multi-level working groups.

The ePLANET project fosters long-term collaboration on energy transition among public authorities. This collaboration is formalised through the ePLANET Joint Agreement, signed near the project's end (Month 36). Representatives from local and regional authorities, spanning beyond the initial pilot regions of the project, have united under this agreement. These participants have been actively engaged with ePLANET across various phases of the project. The agreement reflects a shared vision for actions and initiatives that will accelerate progress towards achieving energy transition goals.

1.1 Organisation of the deliverable

The first section introduces the ePLANET project, emphasising its objectives and expected impacts, mentioning the Joint Agreement as one of the project's main outcomes.

In section 2, the development process of the Joint Agreement is described, from the initial design to the final version approved by the consortium partners involved in WP6.

Section 3 wraps up this deliverable with a thorough summary and insightful reflections that encapsulate the significant implications uncovered throughout the document.

2 Development of the Joint Agreement

To formalise support for the outcomes of ePLANET, all local and regional authorities, along with other stakeholders involved in various stages of the project, must sign a Joint Agreement at the project's conclusion. This agreement embodies a shared vision for actions and initiatives designed to accelerate the achievement of energy transition targets. It serves as a crucial tool for maximising the utilisation of project results by as many local and regional authorities as possible. Additionally, the Joint Agreement institutionalises governance networks, fostering further synergies in energy transition policies.

The initial discussions for developing the Joint Agreement began in early May 2024 (M33). Representatives from CRES, CIMNE, and ICLEI convened for a dedicated meeting to present and exchange ideas on the document's content and requirements. They agreed that the Joint Agreement should be clear and concise, limited to one page, to ensure ease of understanding for interested parties. The first draught concentrated on key points:

1. Commitment to utilising ePLANET digital tools.
2. Endorsement of ePLANET's vision.
3. Dissemination of project outcomes.
4. Acknowledgement of the value of ePLANET's policy recommendations.

In the second round of discussions, an introductory paragraph was developed, and the agreement points were modified as follows:

- Commitment to utilising ePLANET digital tools: Broadened to encompass tools for tracking and managing SECAPs, without a specific mandate to use the ePLANET platform.
- Endorsement of ePLANET's vision: Enhanced to include the development of coordinated activities, reflecting a multi-level approach.
- Items 3 and 4 were reordered to emphasise the valorisation of the Joint Agreement itself at the conclusion.

A third round of discussions occurred a few days later, concluding that the ePLANET Joint Agreement and its signing process should be digital, straightforward, and user-friendly, adopting an "Easy to Read. Easy to Sign" approach. This strategy aims to facilitate the dissemination of the Joint Agreement through social media channels, reaching a broader audience and consequently increasing the number of signatories. During this meeting, partners presented examples of similar actions to illustrate best practices, including:

Technical solution example 1: [Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections | Correlation European Harm Reduction Network \(correlation-net.org\)](#)

The "Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections" calls for a fundamental shift in European drug policies, highlighting the failure of current strategies despite substantial financial investments. European drug policies have not adequately safeguarded public health or safety, with drug use reaching unprecedented levels and new substances frequently entering the EU market. The manifesto criticises war-on-drugs approaches for their inability to curb the influence of organised crime and stresses the need for prevention, treatment, and harm reduction. It points out that services for people who use drugs are underfunded and lack political backing, thereby failing to protect communities effectively.

As the 2024 European elections were close by (June 9th, 2024), the manifesto advocated for a pragmatic and innovative drug policy focused on human rights, aiming to create safer and healthier communities.

As seen in Figure 2-1, the Drug Policy Manifesto was available for signing and downloading in multiple languages, including French, Czech, Italian, and more. This influenced the decision to also have the ePLANET Joint Agreement in multiple languages.

BRIEFINGS & STATEMENTS CIVIL SOCIETY INVOLVEMENT COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT
POLICY & ADVOCACY

Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections

Multiple authors • Europe • 14.03.2024

[Sign the Manifesto](#) [Share Post](#)

For a drug policy that makes Europe safer, healthier, and more just

For a drug policy that makes Europe safer, healthier, and more just

Despite billions spent in drug control, European drug policies have failed to protect the health and safety of our communities.

Drug use is reaching historical records. New substances are entering the EU market every year. War-on-drugs policies have been unable to stop the growing power of organised crime. Evidence shows that prevention, treatment, and harm reduction are necessary to save lives and protect our communities, but services for people who use drugs lack resources and political support.

The 2024 European elections must bring a paradigm shift. This manifesto lays down a vision for a pragmatic, innovative, and human rights-centred European drug policy that will deliver healthier and safer communities. We invite all European civil society organizations, parties, and candidates to endorse the following calls to action.

Together, we will build a drug policy that prepares Europe for the future.

#FutureDrugPolicyEU24

Open To Everyone, Initiated by Correlation – European Harm Reduction Network, NEWNet Enjoying Safer Nightlife.

SIGN AND DOWNLOAD THE MANIFESTO

Also in **French, Czech, Italian, Spanish, German, Hungarian, Romanian, Lithuanian, Estonian, Montenegrin [Bosnian/Croatian/Serbian], Finnish.**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- Ramp up investment in health and social care
- Abandon war-on-drugs policies
- Ensure civil society and community participation
- Explore innovative approaches, including responsible regulation

Already signed by...

RESOURCES

- [download the Manifesto in English](#)
- [download the Manifesto in Czech](#)
- [download the Manifesto in Estonian](#)
- [download the Manifesto in Finnish](#)
- [download the Manifesto in French](#)
- [download the Manifesto in German](#)
- [download the Manifesto in](#)

Figure 2-1 - Webpage of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections

Source: <https://www.correlation-net.org/drug-policy-manifesto-for-the-2024-european-parliament-elections/>

By clicking the "Sign the Manifesto" button, users are directed to a Google Form that briefly explains the objectives of the action and provides simple fields to complete, allowing them to sign in just a few minutes. The clarity and simplicity of this form (Figure 2-2) inspired the design of the online form for the ePLANET Joint Agreement.

For a drug policy that makes Europe safer, healthier, and more just
Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections

Sign the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections

Despite billions spent in drug control, European drug policies have failed to protect the health and safety of our communities.

Drug use is reaching historical records. New substances are entering the EU market every year. War-on-drugs policies have been unable to stop the growing power of organised crime. Evidence shows that prevention, treatment, and harm reduction are necessary to save lives and protect our communities, but services for people who use drugs lack resources and political support.

The 2024 European elections must bring a paradigm shift. This manifesto lays down a vision for a pragmatic, innovative, and human rights-centred European drug policy that will deliver healthier and safer communities. We invite all European civil society organizations, parties, and candidates to endorse the following calls to action.

Together, we will build a drug policy that prepares Europe for the future.

#FutureDrugPolicyEU24

Open To Everyone, Initiated by Correlation - European Harm Reduction Network, NEWNet Enjoying Safer Nightlife and IDPC - International Drug Policy Consortium.

[Sign in to Google](#) to save your progress. [Learn more](#)

* Indicates required question

Email *

Your email

Name *

Your answer

Country *

Your answer

I am a... *

Representative of a Civil Society Organisation

Member of a city council

Mayor

Deputy Mayor

Member of national parliament

MEP or MEP candidate

Candidate [specify]

Other:

Name of the organisation/party you represent *

Your answer

If you represent an organisation and you wish for your logo to be included among the supporters of the Drug Policy Manifesto, please email it in PNG transparent format at communication@correlation-net.org

Do you wish to sign the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections? *

Yes

No

I agree that my name and the name of the organisation are displayed among the supporters of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections. *

I agree

Figure 2-2 - Online form: the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections

Source:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSei592tSYHfMe3k_G7tBs83TT9_BEVgJ_G5xpG1CIHFmCZkeg/viewform

Another important aspect explored by the developers of the Joint Agreement was how similar initiatives were publicised to attract signatories. Drawing from the Drug Policy Manifesto, it was observed that QR codes were commonly used to facilitate mobile access to the form. The Figure 2-3 provides an example of how this promotional strategy was implemented across various social media channels.

Figure 2-3 - Example of dissemination of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections on social media

Source: https://twitter.com/abd_ong/status/1788105947577045305

Technical solution example 2: [Brussels declaration of European mayors: a European policy fit for the future](#)

Another initiative that served as a benchmark for the development of the ePLANET Joint Agreement was the [Declaration of European Mayors](#). The Declaration, developed during the Belgian presidency of the Council of the European Union and co-created by numerous European cities and urban stakeholders, was signed by many Mayors at the “A European Urban Policy Fit for the Future” event on January 24, 2024, organised by the Brussels-Capital Region. It calls for a robust European urban policy and proposes six recommendations for the EU mandate 2024-2029: establishing systematic dialogue with local governments, better integrating and coordinating urban matters, adopting urban-friendly EU regulations, making EU funding more accessible, promoting metropolitan governance, and shifting towards a sustainable urban model. The Brussels-Capital Region champion these recommendations throughout the presidency, and all cities and metropolitan areas were encouraged to sign the declaration.

An interesting aspect of this initiative was displaying a list of all the signatories, as illustrated in Figure 2-4. This concept was also adopted for the ePLANET Joint Agreement, as will be demonstrated later.

The screenshot displays the website for the Brussels Declaration of European Mayors. The top navigation bar includes 'Urban issues', 'Presidency of the Council of the European Union', and 'Declaration of European mayors'. The main content area features a presentation, signatory information, and a list of cities that have signed the declaration. A sidebar on the left lists various urban issues and international events.

Figure 2-4 - Signatories of the Brussels Declaration of European Mayors

Source: <https://perspective.brussels/en/studies-and-observations/presidency-council-european-union/declaration-european-mayors>

The final version of the Joint Agreement was released on June 5, 2024, in the project’s official website and is presented in the following section. It was proposed that signatures be collected at events like the ePLANET final assembly, through the project’s online channels (website and social media), and via partners’ social media channels and newsletters to maximise visibility and promotion.

2.1 Final version of the Joint Agreement

The solution was developed as an online form to ensure the ePLANET Joint Agreement is digital, straightforward, and user-friendly, offering a clear, accessible, and seamless experience for all users.

The first sentence explains the importance of transitioning to a clean energy future due climate change, resource depletion, increasing energy demands, followed by a phrase introducing the Joint Agreement as a key part of the ePLANET project, which represents a collective commitment from participants to achieve this clean energy future.

Next, the agreement specifies that participants must carefully review the following points, indicate their agreement by checking the checkbox, and provide their name, institution, and email address.

The Agreement Points are:

- I confirm my intention to utilise tools to track and analyse the Energy Transition advances.
- I share ePLANET's vision of the development of coordinated activities and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of new figures and roles enhancing multi-level governance coordination for energy transition.
- I acknowledge the value of the policy recommendations at EU level developed by ePLANET and will consider them for potential integration into our future energy policy development or updates.
- I recognise that this agreement facilitates the dissemination of project results among local/regional authorities and stakeholders, serving as a valuable capitalization tool.

Finally, participants are asked to indicate whether they agree to have their name and organisation displayed among the supporters of the ePLANET Joint Agreement on the ePLANET website and in project deliverables.

The following figures, 2-5 and 2-6, illustrate the section dedicated to the ePLANET Joint Agreement on the official project website and the form itself, notably based on the example of the Drug Policy Manifesto for the 2024 European Parliament Elections discussed earlier. Pre-testing sessions were conducted by consortium partners to ensure the correct functionality of the proposed final solution.

The screenshot shows the ePLANET website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ePLANET logo on the left and links for 'Joint Agreement', 'Best Practices', 'Resources', 'News', 'Home', and 'English'. Below the navigation bar, a large teal and purple gradient banner contains the text 'Joint Agreement' and 'ePLANET Joint Agreement for driving the Energy Transition'. A dark blue button labeled 'Sign the Joint Agreement' is centered below the banner. The main content area features a heading: 'Accelerating Energy Transition in the Public Sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities'. Below the heading is a paragraph explaining the need for a sustainable energy system and the purpose of the Joint Agreement. A sub-section titled 'Agreement Points:' lists four bullet points regarding the user's commitment to track energy transition advances, share ePLANET's vision, acknowledge policy recommendations, and disseminate project results.

Joint Agreement
ePLANET Joint Agreement for driving the Energy Transition

Sign the Joint Agreement

Accelerating Energy Transition in the Public Sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities

In the face of escalating climate change, depleting natural resources, and increasing energy demands, the need for a sustainable and resilient energy system has never been more urgent. The following Joint Agreement is part of the ePLANET project summarising a collective commitment to transitioning towards a clean, efficient, and inclusive energy future. This Joint Agreement outlines our shared vision, principles, and actions necessary to drive the energy transition, ensuring a sustainable future for all.

Please read the following points carefully and indicate your agreement by checking the checkbox, then provide your name, institution, and email address.

Agreement Points:

- I confirm my intention to utilise tools to track and analyse the Energy Transition advances.
- I share ePLANET's vision of the development of coordinated activities and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of new figures and roles enhancing multi-level governance coordination for energy transition.
- I acknowledge the value of the policy recommendations at EU level developed by ePLANET and will consider them for potential integration into our future energy policy development or updates.
- I recognise that this agreement facilitates the dissemination of project results among local/regional authorities and stakeholders, serving as a valuable capitalization tool.

Figure 2-5 - Dedicated section for the ePLANET Joint Agreement on the project's website

Joint Agreement
Accelerating Energy Transition in the Public Sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities

Sign the Joint Agreement for driving the the Energy Transition in the Public Sector

In the face of escalating climate change, depleting natural resources, and increasing energy demands, the need for a sustainable and resilient energy system has never been more urgent. The following Joint Agreement is part of the ePLANET project summarising a collective commitment to transitioning towards a clean, efficient, and inclusive energy future. This Joint Agreement outlines our shared vision, principles, and actions necessary to drive the energy transition, ensuring a sustainable future for all.

Please read the following points carefully and indicate your agreement by checking the checkbox, then provide your name, institution, and email address.

Agreement Points:

- I confirm my intention to utilise tools to track and analyse the Energy Transition advances.
- I share ePLANET's vision of the development of coordinated activities and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of new figures and roles enhancing multi-level governance coordination for energy transition.
- I acknowledge the value of the policy recommendations at EU level developed by ePLANET and will consider them for potential integration into our future energy policy development or updates.
- I recognise that this agreement facilitates the dissemination of project results among local/regional authorities and stakeholders, serving as a valuable capitalization tool.

Email *

Your email

Name and Surname: *

Your answer

Name of the organisation/entity you represent: *

Your answer

Do you want to sign the ePLANET Joint Agreement? *

Yes

I agree that my name and the name of the organisation are displayed among the supporters of the ePLANET Joint Agreement, in the ePLANET website and the project deliverables. *

I agree

I disagree

A copy of your responses will be emailed to the address you provided.

Clear form

Figure 2-6 - Form for the ePLANET Joint Agreement

Based on the insights from the [Declaration of European Mayors](#), it was decided to display on the website the current number of signatories and their names, as long as they have agreed to this when completing the form and signing the Joint Agreement. Figure 2-7 illustrates how this is being implemented. This approach is crucial for enhancing the visibility of current signatories, thereby showcasing their active involvement and commitment to driving forward the agenda of energy transition and sustainability.

The screenshot shows the ePLANET website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the ePLANET logo on the left and links for 'Joint Agreement', 'Best Practices', 'Resources', 'News', 'Home', and a language selector set to 'English'. Below the navigation bar is a prominent blue button that says 'Sign the Joint Agreement'. Underneath this button, a white box with a light blue border contains the text 'They have already signed:' followed by a list of 253 public authorities that have signed the agreement. The list includes various municipalities and regional agencies from across Europe, such as Zlínský Kraj, Ajuntament de Girona, and many others.

They have already signed:

So far, 253 public authorities have already signed the ePLANET Joint Agreement. Among others:

Zlínský Kraj; Ajuntament de Girona; Municipality of Heraklion; Statutární město Zlín; South East Energy Agency (Kilkenny); Agency for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Protection of Bucharest; Comunidade Intermunicipal do Tâmega e Sousa; Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia; Union of Bulgarian Black Sea Local Authorities; Consell Comarcal del Baix Llobregat; Municipality of Chania; Agentura krajského energetického managementu Karlovarského kraje; Municipality of Fylk; Olomoucký kraj; Region Bílé Karpaty; Consell Comarcal de la Noguera; Consell Comarcal del Pallars Jussà; Město Bojkovice; Město Brumov-Bylnice; Město Fryšták; Město Hluk; Město Holešov; Město Hulín; Město Karolinka; Město Kroměříž; Město Luhačovice; Město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm; Město Slavičín; Město Trnava; Město Uherské Hradiště; Město Uherský Brod; Město Uherský Ostroh; Město Valašské Klobouky; Město Vizovice; Město Zubří; Městys Nový Hrozenkov; Městys Pozlovice; Municipality of Anogia; Municipality of Apokoronas; Municipality of Hersonissos; Municipality of Kantanou-Selinou; Municipality of Minoa Pediada; Municipality of Platania; Ajuntament de Puigcerdà; Obec Bohuslavice u Zlína; Ajuntament de Ripoll; Ajuntament de Celrà; Ajuntament de Torroella de Montgrí; Ajuntament Cornellà del Terri; Ajuntament d'Agullana; Ajuntament d'Aiguaviva; Ajuntament d'Albons; Ajuntament d'Amer; Ajuntament d'Anglès; Ajuntament d'Avinyonet de Puigventós; Ajuntament d'Esponellà; Ajuntament d'Ogassa; Ajuntament d'Olot; Ajuntament d'Ullastret; Ajuntament de Bescara; Ajuntament de Begur; Ajuntament de Bellcaire d'Empordà; Ajuntament de Bescanó; Ajuntament de Beuda; Ajuntament d'Ullà; Ajuntament de Blanes; Ajuntament de Cabanes; Ajuntament de Calonge i Sant Antoni; Ajuntament de Canet d'Adri; Ajuntament de Capmany; Ajuntament de Cassà de la Selva; Ajuntament de Castellfollit de la Roca; Ajuntament de Cistella; Ajuntament de Colomers; Ajuntament de Das; Ajuntament de Forallac; Ajuntament de Fornells de la Selva; Ajuntament de Garrigoles; Ajuntament de Gombren; Ajuntament de Gualta; Ajuntament de Juià; Ajuntament de la Bisbal d'Empordà; Ajuntament de la Cellera de Ter; Ajuntament de La Pera; Ajuntament de la Tallada d'Empordà; Ajuntament de la Vall d'en Bas; Ajuntament de La Vall de Bianya; Ajuntament de Les Preses; Ajuntament de Lladó; Ajuntament de Llagostera; Ajuntament de Llambilles; Ajuntament de Llançà; Ajuntament de Maçanet de Cabrenys; Ajuntament de Madremanya; Ajuntament de Maià de Montcal; Ajuntament de Meranges; Ajuntament de Mont-ras; Ajuntament de Palafrugell; Ajuntament de Palau de Santa Eulàlia; Ajuntament de Palau-sator; Ajuntament de Palol de Revardit; Ajuntament de Pals;

Figure 2-7 - Current signatories of the ePLANET Joint Agreement

The dissemination of the ePLANET Joint Agreement is crucial for extending the project's outcomes widely and attracting the highest possible number of signatories. To achieve this, the digital solution is being promoted through the project's social media channels, posters at strategic events, and via partners' social media and newsletters. Figure 2-8 below illustrates an example of a poster used at the project's final assembly in early June 2024, featuring a QR Code to facilitate signing via mobile phones. The dissemination and communication process will continue until the official project conclusion.

Joint Agreement
ePLANET Joint Agreement for driving the Energy Transition

Accelerating Energy Transition in the Public Sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities

In the face of escalating climate change, depleting natural resources, and increasing energy demands, the need for a sustainable and resilient energy system has never been more urgent. The following Joint Agreement is part of the ePLANET project summarising a collective commitment to transitioning towards a clean, efficient, and inclusive energy future. This Joint Agreement outlines our shared vision, principles, and actions necessary to drive the energy transition, ensuring a sustainable future for all.

Please read the following points carefully and indicate your agreement by checking the checkbox, then provide your name, institution, and email address.

Agreement Points:

- I confirm my intention to utilise tools to track and analyse the Energy Transition advances.
- I share ePLANET's vision of the development of coordinated activities and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of new figures and roles enhancing multi-level governance coordination for energy transition.
- I acknowledge the value of the policy recommendations at EU level developed by ePLANET and will consider them for potential integration into our future energy policy development or updates.
- I recognise that this agreement facilitates the dissemination of project results among local/regional authorities and stakeholders, serving as a valuable capitalization tool.

Figure 2-8 - Poster with a QR Code disseminating the ePLANET Joint Agreement

3 Final considerations

ePLANET has yielded significant outcomes, with the Joint Agreement standing out as a cornerstone achievement. The project has introduced a robust governance framework leveraging digital tools to harmonise information sharing, essential for coordinated efforts towards energy transition across the European public sector. ePLANET plays an important role in advancing ET within Europe by addressing critical challenges through innovative approaches and collaborative partnerships.

The ePLANET Joint Agreement symbolises a collective commitment among public authorities and stakeholders to utilise project tools and outcomes, facilitating enhanced multi-level governance for energy transition coordination.

The Joint Agreement serves as a unifying mechanism, aligning diverse stakeholders behind a shared vision of accelerating progress towards sustainable energy goals. It provides local, regional, and EU-level authorities with a structured platform to leverage project outcomes effectively.

Designed with usability in mind, the ePLANET Joint Agreement is accessible through the ePLANET official website, streamlining the signing process for stakeholders across Europe. Continuously updating the list of signatory institutions on the website enhances transparency and reinforces commitment among participants.

Initiatives like the ePLANET Joint Agreement are crucial for Europe's energy transition agenda. By fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among various stakeholders, these initiatives not only promote innovation but also ensure that the benefits of energy transition are equitably distributed across regions. They strengthen the resilience of local economies, improve environmental sustainability, and contribute to achieving Europe's ambitious climate and energy targets.

As the ePLANET Project moves to its completion, the ongoing commitment of signatories and stakeholders is vital in sustaining momentum and driving lasting change towards a greener and more resilient Europe.